

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS, PROBLEM SOLVING SKILLS, AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: A CORRELATIONAL RESEARCH APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the relationship between reading comprehension skills, problem-solving skills, and academic achievement in Grade 10 students. Using stratified-random sampling, 70 participants were selected, and the data was analyzed using correlation, regression, and ANOVA. The study found a significant and moderate correlation between reading comprehension and problem-solving skills, indicating that as reading comprehension improves, so does problem-solving ability. There was also a strong correlation between reading comprehension skills, problem-solving skills towards the academic achievement, suggesting that better reading comprehension and problem-solving is linked to higher academic achievement. Age played a significant role, with older students demonstrating higher levels of both reading comprehension and problem-solving skills. Gender differences were observed in reading comprehension, with males outperforming females, but no significant gender differences were found in problem-solving skills. This concludes that reading comprehension is an indicator to the problem-solving skills and academic achievement of the students.

Keywords: *Reading Comprehension, Problem-solving, Academic Achievement*

INTRODUCTION

“The first stage in resolving an issue is to acknowledge its existence,” says Zig Ziglar. This emphasizes the importance of identifying and accepting the existence of an issue before taking further action to address it. Everyday people encounter difficulties, challenges or problems wherein it calls for a solution and a need for improvement and intervention that depends to the areas the matter is concerned. In academics, students experience lots of problems such as having the hard time to comprehend and to get the right solution of the given mathematical word problems. In fact, the Philippine Star reports the Program for International Students Assessment (PISA) test results, revealed that Philippines was ranked 76th out of 81 countries participating in reading comprehension in 2022. Indicators of the test implies top-performing students in the country did not go up in percentage points, while low-performing students registered a 4.3 percent decline in reading comprehension proficiency levels with respect to the result of PISA in 2018 where Philippines ranked 79th place, (Servallos,2023). Furthermore, in the aspect of mathematics the Philippines ranked sixth lowest after ranked the second lowest in 2018 still in Program for International Assessment test.

Consequently, to better understand a text, reading is necessary since it exposes the real meaning of the hidden ideas or concepts that a text contains (Akyol, 2006; Akyol & Boyaci-Altinay, 2019). In addition, a study conducted by Pearce, Skinner, Brunn and Lopez-Mohler (2013) as cited by Moleko & Mosimege (2020) found that the teachers responded that the students have difficulty in solving word problems and reading ability affects it less particularly in the United States where the study is conducted. However, in a study of Nicolas and Emata (2018) stated that the students problem solving was developed with the aid of an integrative approach through reading comprehension. It can also be seen that the level of proficiency of a student in reading comprehension can influence how students understand or analyze a word problem especially in the field of mathematics. With these adequate contrasting findings, it is evident that reading comprehension skills may have or may not have a significant impact on problem solving skills of the students.

Similar situation has been observed among the students in the Saint Joseph College of Sindangan Incorporated which the students have encountered difficulty in extracting the right solution and answer to the given mathematical word problems. It is also observed that the students had a hard time in understanding and comprehending what the given mathematical text implies. With these, it is important to know the relationship between the reading comprehension to the problem-solving ability of the students would be.

Subsequently, with the context mentioned, the researchers would like to further determine the relationship of reading comprehension skills, problem-solving skills as well as the academic achievement of the Grade 10 students in the Saint Joseph College of Sindangan Incorporated S.Y. 2023-2024. Moreover, this research provides fulfillment for the benefits of the students, teachers, school administrators and etc. With the findings and recommendation of the study the above-mentioned beneficiaries will be guided on

the relationship of reading comprehension skill, problem-solving skills and academic achievement of the students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the significant relationship between reading comprehension proficiency, problem-solving skills, and academic achievement of the Grade 10 students in the Saint Joseph College of Sindangan Incorporated S.Y.2023-2024.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following queries:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender
 2. What is the proficiency level of reading comprehension skills of the students?
 3. What is the level of Problem-Solving skills of the students?
 4. What is the Academic Achievement of the students?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills of the students?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and the academic achievement of the students?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and academic achievement of the students?
 8. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the students across their profile in terms of age?
 9. Is there a significant difference in the problem-solving of the students across their profile in terms of age?
 10. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the students across their profile in terms of gender?
 11. Is there a significant difference in the problem-solving of the students across their profile in terms of gender?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study mainly used a quantitative design to determine the relationship between Reading Comprehension Proficiency, Problem-Solving Skills, and Academic Achievement of Grade 10 students. Typically, the variables in this study (independent and dependent variables) were measured using an instrument by means of survey questionnaires. The methods also involved description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered. It usually entails the relationship between the variables under studied which are non-manipulative variables.

The researchers specifically used a correlational study to produce a valid result that would answer the objectives of conducting the study. Correlational design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or

manipulating any of them (Bhandari, 2022). The data gathered were integrated using statistical tools to determine or to discover relationships among variables involved in the research endeavor.

The information obtained from the study utilizing the quantitative method contingent on a better way on the relationship between the Reading Comprehension and Problem-Solving Skills of the students will yield to results thus, will be able to attain the goals of the study.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in the study is one set of questionnaires for the respondents. The questionnaire for the respondents is consists of three parts:

Part I.

Deal with the respondents' personal profile and identity. This part elicits data on name (optional), age, and gender.

Part II.

Deal on the proficiency level of the reading comprehension skills of the Grade 10 students. This part of test the researchers created a self-made multiple questions adapting some text or stories from the textbook and then formulate questions from it. There are 20 items for this part. Also, adapted and modified the scale for reading comprehension performance of Alieto and Buslon (2019) to set the description of the scores based on the questionnaires answered by the respondents.

Part III.

Deal on the level of problem-solving skills of the Grade 10 students. This part of questionnaire composed of 20 multiple choice items which are made by the researchers having some textbook and available online materials which the concepts were get. Moreover, the study adapted and modified the scaling of the level of problem-solving skills of the students by Alcantara and Bacsá (2017) to explicate the scores got by the respondents.

Before the set of questionnaires were distributed and administered to the 88 Grade 10 students, a pilot test was conducted with 18 students who are also Grade 10 but not included to the identified 70 participants of the study. In this way, the instrument will be validated and will ensure its reliability so that it would be aligned to the objectives of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preparation phase. In this stage, the participants needed in the study which is the Grade 10 students is identified by the researchers. The sampling used is stratified

sampling which was utilized to choose the number of respondents needed in the study. With this, the researchers have chosen the two sections of Grade 10 students S.Y. 2023-2024. The researchers sent a letter to the Junior High Principal, to ask permission to conduct the study among the chosen respondents.

Quantitative Instrument. The researchers made a set of multiple-choice questions having 20 items in reading comprehension skills and another 20 items in problem-solving skills. In which the concepts are within the capacity of Grade 10 students. The reliability, validity and internal consistency of the test items was also ensured through a pilot test and consultation of the panel of experts in the College of Arts, Sciences and Teacher Education.

Pilot testing phase. The researchers conducted the pilot testing of the survey questionnaire to the 18 students, having 9 students in each section of Grade 10 and the researchers assessed and asked their comments about the survey administered to them. Beforehand, the researchers explained the research endeavor and ask the consent of these participants of the pilot testing. Then, the researchers would compute, analyze, and interpret the data gathered in this phase.

Survey. The researchers made a formal letter addressed to the parents of the students asking their permission to let their child participate and answer the survey questionnaire. Another letter to the math teacher of the Grade 10 students to humbly asked for some allotted time to conduct the survey since it needs at least an hour to answer the questions in the survey. The researchers used the survey questionnaire to gather information from the chosen respondents of the study. Lastly, researchers followed the ethical way in getting the current test scores of the students in English and Math that will be served as the data for academic achievement.

Statistical Treatment

1. To test the reliability of the instrument (survey questionnaires) in the pilot testing phase, *Cronbach Alpha* was used.

2. To determine the answer to the research question number 1 which is concerned with the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, and club affiliations, *Frequency Count and Percentage*, and *Mean* statistical tools were utilized.

3. To answer the research question number 2, 3 and 4 all about the proficiency level on reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills as perceived by the respondents, the *Frequency Count and Percentage*, *Weighted Mean*, *Standard Deviation*, *Scale for reading comprehension performance* (Alieto & Buslon, 2019), *Scale for problem-solving performance* (Alcantara & Bacsa, 2017) and *Descriptor Baseline for the Academic Achievement* of the grading system implemented by the DepEd (Tadios, L.K.A., & et al., 2022) are utilized. Below are the tables which demonstrate the scaling, the range of scores and the interpretation or descriptor that researchers adapted and modified.

Table 1*Five Point Scale on the Level of reading comprehension performance*

Range of Score	Description
17-20	Very Proficient
13-16	Proficient
9-12	Somehow Proficient
5-8	Less Proficient
0-4	Not Proficient

Table 2*Five Point Scale on the Level of problem-solving skills of the students*

Range of Score	Level of Problem-Solving Skills
17-20	Superior
13-16	Above Average
9-12	Average
5-8	Below Average
0-4	Poor

Table 3*Descriptor Baseline of Academic Achievement of the students*

Scale of Percentile Test Scores	Descriptor
90 – 100	Outstanding
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	Satisfactory
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	Did not Meet the Expectations

4. To determine the significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills, problem-solving skills and academic achievement of the students which is reflected in the statement of the problem number 4,5, & 6 the researchers used the statistical tools such as *Pearson Product Momentum Correlation (PPMC)*, *Regression* and *ANOVA*.

5. To answer the research question 7, 8, 9 & 10 regarding the significant difference between the profile of the respondents and their reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills, *Analysis of Variance* and *Cohens' D* tool were utilized.

The assumptions of the parametric tests are tested by the researchers before utilizing it in the data analysis. Further, these assumptions are met in this research endeavor.

RESULTS

This research was intended for exploring the significant relationship of reading comprehension, problem-solving skills, and academic achievement of Grade 10 students. After the success of undertaking the methods specifically the data gathering phase, calculations were made by the researchers. This chapter demonstrates the answer to the problem of the study found in the first chapter that would yield to results and conclusions. This chapter also highlights the analysis and interpretation of data gathered.

Results of the Pilot Study

Table 1 presents the scores of the participants of the pilot study both in reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills. In the reading comprehension column demonstrates that among eighteen participants, eleven (11) got scores ranging from 17 – 20, four (4) got scores ranging from 13 – 16, two (2) got scores ranging from 9 – 12, and one (1) got scores ranging from 5 – 8. On the other hand, in the column of problem-solving among eighteen participants, 3 three got scores ranging from 17 – 20, seven (7) got scores ranging from 13 – 16, six (6) got scores ranging from 9 – 12, and two (2) got scores ranging from 5 – 8.

Table 1
Distribution of Scores of the Participants of the Pilot Testing

Scores	Frequency	
	Reading Comprehension	Problem-solving
17 – 20	11	3
13 – 16	4	7
9 – 12	2	6
5 – 8	1	2
0 – 4	0	0
Total	18	18

Table 1 presents the results of the pilot testing that were calculated through using Cronbach Alpha to test the reliability and the consistency of the items in the survey questionnaire both the reading comprehension and problem-solving questions. Since, there are a lot of variation of Cronbach Alpha, the researchers utilized the formula from

the video tutorial of Dr. Eugene O’Loughlin in the year 2020 $\alpha = \left(\frac{k}{k-1} \right) \left(\frac{s_y^2 - \sum s_i^2}{s_y^2} \right)$.

The internal consistency of the initial questionnaire is presented in Table 1 after it was administered to 18 student – participants. The reading comprehension and problem-solving items has equal alpha coefficient of 0.824 and 0.766 respectively which interpreted as good and acceptable. These indicate that the questionnaires’ content is reliable and does not need further revisions. This means that the instrument used in this study is appropriate and valid.

Table 2
Cronbach Alpha Result

	Alpha Coefficient	Number of items	Internal Consistency
Reading Comprehension	0.824	20	good
Problem-Solving	0.766	20	acceptable

The result of the pilot test allowed the researchers to proceed to the conduct of the final survey. This survey was conducted to the sample which is the 70 respondents utilizing the same questionnaire used in the pilot test. With this, the researchers could gather enough data that would obtain comprehensive details which are essential to achieve the specific goals of the research endeavor.

Problem 1.1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age?

Table 2 presents the age of the 70 selected respondents. Based on the results, twenty-five (25) respondents have an age of 15 which corresponds to 35.72%, forty (40) have an age of 16 which corresponds to 57.14% and five (5) have an age of 17. This only shows that most of the respondents’ age is 15, which implies that majority of the Grade 10 students in SJCSI are ages 15.

Table 2
Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
15	25	35.72
16	40	57.14
17	5	7.14
Total	70	100

Problem 1.2. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of gender?

Table 3 illustrates the gender identity of the respondents of the 70 selected participants of the study. Based on the data, forty (40) of the respondents is male which corresponds to 57.14% and out of 70 respondents there are thirty (30) who are female which is 42.86% of the sample size.

This only shows that there are more male respondents compare to female, which has a difference of 10 in frequency.

Table 3

Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
Male	40	57.14
Female	30	42.86
Total	70	100

Problem 2. What is the level of reading comprehension skills of the students?

Table 4 shows that out of 70 participants of the study forty-one got the scores ranging from 17 – 20 equivalent to 58.57% of the sample size, which is very proficient in reading comprehension, twenty students got scores ranging from 13 – 16 equivalent to 28.57% which is considered as proficient, and five got scores ranging from 9 – 12 that corresponds to 7.14% that is considered as somehow proficient. Whilst one student got the score within the range of 5 – 8 that corresponds to the 1.43% which is identified as less proficient, and three out of seventy students got the score within the range of 0 – 4 that corresponds to 4.29% of the sample size which is identified as not proficient in terms of reading comprehension skills. Equally important, the table 8 illustrates the overall weighted mean is 16.17 or 16 which belongs to the ranging scores of 13 – 16 and identified as proficient in terms of reading comprehension; also, has a standard deviation of 3.83 which signifies that the scores of the students in reading comprehension varied and somehow spread out.

Table 4

Level of Reading Comprehension

Range of Score	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Description
17 – 20	41	58.57	Very Proficient
13 – 16	20	28.57	Proficient
9 – 12	5	7.14	Somehow Proficient
5 – 8	1	1.43	Less Proficient

0 – 4	3	4.29	Not Proficient
Total	70	100	

Overall weighted mean = 16.17 *SD = 3.83*

Problem 3. What is the level of reading comprehension skills of the students?

Table 5 demonstrates the performance of the problem-solving of the students with respect to the scores got from the test. Twenty-nine (29) students which corresponds to the 41.43% of the sample size performed well in the problem solving which got scores ranging from 17 – 20 and identified as superior, twenty (20) got scores ranging from 13 – 16 which is equivalent to 28.57% of the participants that can be classified as above average, sixteen (16) or 22.86% of the students got scores ranging from 9 – 12 which is described as average, four (4) students got the scores ranging from 5 – 8 which is described as below average, and one (1) out seventy participants got the scores ranging from 0 – 4 which is interpreted as poor in terms of problem-solving skills. Moreover, the overall weighted mean of the students is 14.61 which has level of problem-solving skills above average and the standard deviation is 3.91 which signifies that most students belong to proficient level which the test scores varied and somewhat spread out.

Table 5
Level of Problem-Solving Skills

Range of Score	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Description
17 – 20	32	45.71	Superior
13 – 16	19	27.14	Above Average
9 – 12	14	20	Average
5 – 8	3	4.29	Below Average
0 – 4	2	2.86	Poor
Total	70	100	

Overall weighted mean = 14.41 *SD = 3.87*

Problem 4. What is the academic achievement of the students?

Table 6 illustrates the academic achievement of the students using the average of their test scores in the English and Math subject respectively. Out of 70 students twenty-nine (29) got scores ranging from 90 – 100 that corresponds to 41.43% which is interpreted as outstanding, eighteen (18) got scores ranging from 85 – 89 which corresponds to 25.71% which is very satisfactory, twelve (12) got scores grade ranging from 80 – 84 that corresponds to 17.14% which is satisfactory, nine (9) got scores ranging from 75 – 79 that corresponds to 12.86% which is fairly satisfactory and two (2) got scores below 75 which corresponds to 2.86% which classified as did not meet the expectations; with mean of 86.43 and standard deviation of 5.87. This implies that most students have a very satisfactory academic achievement which the percentile scores varied.

Table 6
Academic Achievement of the Students

Scale of Test Scores (percentile)	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptor
90 – 100	29	41.43	Outstanding
85 – 89	18	25.71	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	12	17.14	Satisfactory
75 – 79	9	12.86	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	2	2.86	Did not meet the expectations
Total	70	100	
<i>Overall weighted mean = 86.43</i>			<i>SD = 5.87</i>

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and problem solving skills of the students?

Table 7 presents the result from the correlation test using the Pearson Product Momentum Correlation. The reading comprehension and problem-solving has correlation coefficient [*r*] of 0.63 which is between 0.5 and 0.7 which is classified and interpreted as moderate correlation.

Table 7

PPMC Test Result

Variables	reading comprehension	problem-solving	Interpretation
reading comprehension	1	0.63	Moderately
problem-solving	0.63	1	Correlated

Legend: 0.9 > r < 1 - very highly correlated, 0.7 > r < 0.9 - highly correlated, 0.5 > r < 0.7 - moderately correlated, 0.3 > r < 0.5 - low correlation

Table 8 provides valuable insights into the strength of the relationship of reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills in the regression model. The multiple R is 0.629 or 0.63 which has an equal value of correlation coefficient (table 10), this represents the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the two variables, since Multiple R is 0.629 it indicates a moderate positive correlation. R square is the coefficient of determination which has a value of 0.397, it signifies that approximately 39.7% of the variance of problem-solving is explained by the reading comprehension. Adjusted R Square is 0.388 which is slightly lower than the R Square due to the adjustment for the number of predictors, but it implies the same thing as R Square. Standard error of 3.07% signifies that the data in regression model's prediction are closer to the actual values, it is more likely to be accurate. For the number of observations which is 70 entails that there are total of 70 data points used in regression analysis.

Table 8

Regression Analysis Result

Regression Statistics Summary

Multiple R	0.629
R Square	0.397
Adjusted R Square	0.388
Standard Error	3.07
Observations	70

Table 9 reveals the summary of the Analysis of Variance test that gives an insights on the relationship and its significance. The degree of freedom (df) is 69. SS stands for the Sum of Squares, which indicates the variability explained by the regression model, in the regression SS is 421.945 and in residual is 641.4264 MS stands for Mean Square, which is calculated by dividing the sum of squares by the degrees of freedom, regression MS is 421.945 while the residual MS is 9.433. Moreover, the F value is 44.73 which is the test statistic for the ANOVA test; this indicates somewhat stronger relationship between the reading comprehension and problem-solving skills.

Consequently, the significance F is 5.15E-09 which is equivalent to 5.15×10^{-9} this indicates an extremely less value, suggesting strong evidence against the null hypothesis. This results suggests that the reading comprehension has a significant impact on the problem-solving skills of the students.

Table 9
ANOVA Test Result

ANOVA	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	421.945	421.945	44.73196	5.15E-09
Residual	68	641.4264	9.433		
Total	69	1063.371			

Analysis and Interpretation of Results

Table 10 shows the summary of the results of the correlation and analysis of variance. The correlation coefficient is 0.63 which indicates a moderately positive correlation. Moreover, the Significance F is also referring to p-value, since 5.15×10^{-9} is an extremely low value. With this, since p-value is less than 0.05 (level of significance) this means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that there is a significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills. This yield result is supported by the related studies mentioned in the chapter II component of this research like the study of Auzar (2018) found out that the capability of students to understand the language of mathematical word problem is relayed to the ability to read for comprehension. Similarly, a study found that problem-solving skills of the students are dependent to their reading comprehension skills wherein it paved the way to the importance of vocabulary and the main idea in learning problem-solving, (Timario, 2020).

Table 10

Summary of the Result between reading comprehension and problem-solving

ANOVA & PPMC				
Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Significance F	p-value	Interpretation
Reading Comprehension Problem-Solving	0.63	5.15×10^{-9}	< 0.05	significant

d.f. = 68 at 0.05 level of significance

Problem 6. Is there a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and the academic achievement of the students?

Table 11 illustrates the result from the correlation test using the Pearson Product Momentum Correlation. The reading comprehension and academic achievement of students has correlation coefficient [r] of 0.73 which is between 0.7 and 0.9 which is classified and interpreted as high correlation.

Table 11

PPMC Test Result

Variables	reading comprehension	academic achievement	Interpretation
reading comprehension	1	0.73	Highly
academic achievement	0.73	1	Correlated

Legend: $0.9 > r < 1$ - very highly correlated, $0.7 > r < 0.9$ - highly correlated, $0.5 > r < 0.7$ - moderately correlated, $0.3 > r < 0.5$ - low correlation

Table 12 provides valuable insights into the strength of the relationship of reading comprehension skills and academic achievement in the regression model. The multiple R is 0.727 which has an equal value of correlation coefficient, this represents the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the reading comprehension and academic achievement, since Multiple R is 0.727 it indicates a high positive correlation. R square is the coefficient of determination which has a value of 0.528, it signifies that approximately 52.8% of the variance of academic achievement is explained by the reading comprehension. Adjusted R Square is 0.521 which is slightly lower than the R Square due to the adjustment for the number of predictors, but it implies the same thing as R Square. Standard error of 4.065% signifies that the data in regression model's prediction are closer to the actual values, it is more likely to be accurate. For the number of observations which is 70 entails that there are total of 70 data points used in regression analysis.

Table 12

Regression Analysis Result

Regression Statistics Summary

Multiple R	0.727
R Square	0.528
Adjusted R Square	0.521
Standard Error	4.065
Observations	70

Table 13 demonstrates the summary of the Analysis of Variance test that gives an insights on the relationship and its significance. The degree of freedom (df) is 69. SS stands for the Sum of Squares, which indicates the variability explained by the regression model; in the regression SS is 1256.795 and in residual is 1123.848. MS stands for Mean Square, which is calculated by dividing the sum of squares by the degrees of freedom, regression MS is 1256.795 while the residual MS is 16.527. In addition, the F value is 76.044 which is the test statistic for the ANOVA test; this indicates a stronger relationship between the reading comprehension and academic achievement.

Subsequently, the significance F is 1.08E-12 which is equivalent to 1.08×10^{-12} this indicates an extremely less value, suggesting very strong evidence against the null hypothesis. These results suggest that the reading comprehension has a significant impact on the academic achievement of the students.

Table 13

ANOVA Test Result of reading comprehension and academic achievement

ANOVA					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	1256.795	1256.795	76.044	1.08E-12
Residual	68	1123.848	16.527		
Total	69	2380.643			

Analysis and Interpretation of Results

Table 14 shows the summary of the results of the correlation and analysis of variance. The correlation coefficient is 0.73 which indicates a highly positive correlation. Moreover, the Significance F which is 1.08×10^{-12} also refers to p-value is an extremely low value. With this, since p-value is less than 0.05 (level of significance) this means that the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. This is suggesting that there is a significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills and academic achievement. This implies that reading comprehension has a great impact in the academic achievement of the students. This is also supported by the study of Jala in 2020 which asserts that reading comprehension is a contributory factor to the development of the overall academic performance of the students.

Table 14

Summary of the Result between Reading Comprehension and Academic achievement

ANOVA & PPMC				
Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Significance F	p-value	Interpretation
Reading Comprehension Academic achievement	0.73	1.08×10^{-12}	< 0.05	Significant

d.f. = 68 at 0.05 level of significance

Problem 7. Is there a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and academic achievement of the students?

Table 15 reveals the result from the correlation test using the Pearson Product Momentum Correlation. The problem-solving and academic achievement of students has correlation coefficient [*r*] of 0.72 which is between 0.7 and 0.9 which is classified and interpreted as high correlation. This signifies that problem-solving skills is highly correlated with the academic achievement of the students.

Table 15

PPMC Test Result

Variables	problem-solving	academic achievement	Interpretation
Problem-solving	1	0.72	Highly
academic achievement	0.72	1	Correlated

Legend: $0.9 > r < 1$ - very highly correlated, $0.7 > r < 0.9$ - highly correlated, $0.5 > r < 0.7$ - moderately correlated, $0.3 > r < 0.5$ - low correlation

Table 15 gives valuable insights into the strength of the relationship of problem-solving skills and academic achievement in the regression model. The multiple R is 0.724 which has an equal value of correlation coefficient, this represents the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the problem-solving and academic achievement, since Multiple R is 0.724 it indicates a moderate positive correlation. R square is the coefficient of determination which has a value of 0.524, it signifies that approximately 52.4% of the variance of academic achievement is supported by the problem-solving. Adjusted R Square is 0.517 which is slightly lower than the R Square due to the adjustment for the number of predictors, but it implies the same thing as R Square. Standard error of 4.08% signifies that the data in regression model's prediction are more likely closer to the actual values, it appears to be accurate. For the number of observations which is 70 entails that there are total of 70 data points used in regression analysis.

Table 16

Regression Analysis Result between problem-solving and academic achievement

Regression Statistics Summary	
Multiple R	0.724
R Square	0.524
Adjusted R Square	0.517
Standard Error	4.08
Observations	70

Table 17 shows the summary of the Analysis of Variance test that gives an insights on the relationship of the variables involve and its significance. The degrees of freedom (df) is 69. SS stands for the Sum of Squares, which indicates the variability explained by the regression model; in the regression SS is 1248.48 and in residual is 1132.163. MS stands for Mean Square, which is calculated by dividing the sum of squares by the degrees of freedom, regression MS is 1248.48 while the residual MS is 16.649. In addition, the F value is 74.986 which is the test statistic for the ANOVA test; this indicates a strong relationship between the reading comprehension and academic achievement.

Equally important, the significance F is 1.392E-12 which is equal to 1.39×10^{-12} this indicates an extremely less value, implying very strong evidence against the null hypothesis. This results suggests that the problem-solving skills has a significant impact on the academic achievement of the students.

Table 17

ANOVA Test Result of problem-solving and academic achievement

ANOVA					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	1248.48	1248.48	74.986	1.39E-12
Residual	68	1132.163	16.649		
Total	69	2380.643			

Analysis and Interpretation of Results

Table 18 reveals the summary of the results of the correlation and analysis of variance. The correlation coefficient is 0.72 which indicates a moderately positive correlation. Moreover, the Significance F which is 1.39×10^{-12} (also refers to p-value) is an extremely low value. With this, since p-value is less than 0.05 (level of significance) this means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This signifies that there is a significant

relationship between the problem-solving skills and academic achievement. This endures and emphasizes in the study of Jala in the year 2020 where it is found out that the overall academic performance or the academic achievement of the students is influenced on their skills which includes the problem-solving skills (stated in chapter 2).

Table 18

Summary of the Result between reading comprehension and academic achievement

ANOVA & PPMC				
Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Significance F	p-value	Interpretation
Problem-solving Academic achievement	0.72	1.39×10^{-12}	< 0.05	significant

d.f. = 68 at 0.05 level of significance

Problem 8. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the students across their profile in terms of age?

Table 19 shows a medium significant difference ($d = 0.70$) between age groups of the students namely: 15, 16 and 17. Students who are 15 years old has an overall mean of 17.33 (very proficient in reading comprehension skills) and standard deviation of 2.19, students who are in the 16 years of age has an overall mean of 14.83 (proficient in reading comprehension) and standard deviation of 4.64, and students who are 17 years old has an overall mean of 18.6 (very proficient in reading comprehension) and standard deviation of 1.52; means that 17 years old performed significantly better or has a higher level of reading comprehension skills compared with 15 and 16 years old with mean difference of 1.27 and 3.77 respectively.

The results of the single-factor ANOVA are the following: F-value is 5.06, critical F-value (F crit) is 3.13 at a significance level of 0.05. Since, the F-value obtained (5.06) exceeds the critical value (3.13) this suggest that a significant difference exists between the age groups in terms of reading comprehension skills. Furthermore, the p-value associated with the F-test is equal to 0.00896 which is below the typical significance level of 0.05, this indicates strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in reading comprehension skills across different age groups. Hence, there is a significant difference in reading comprehension skills among the age groups of 15, 16, and 17.

TABLE 19*ANOVA of Reading Comprehension in terms of Age*

Age	Mean	SD	Observation	Df	F	F crit	p-value	Cohen's D
15	17.33	2.19	30					
16	14.83	4.64	35	67	5.06	3.13	0.008965353	0.70
17	18.6	1.52	5					

Problem 9. Is there a significant difference in the problem-solving of the students across their profile in terms of age?

Table 20 conveys a medium significant difference ($d = 0.58$) among the age groups of the students namely: 15,16 and 17. Students who are 15 years of age has an overall mean of 15.73 (above average in terms of problem-solving) and standard deviation of 3.31, students who are 16 years of age has an overall mean of 13.57 (above average in terms of problem-solving) and standard deviation of 4.24, and students who are 17 years of age has an overall mean of 17 (superior in terms of problem-solving) and standard deviation of 2.83. This means that 17 years old performed significantly better compared to 15 and 16 years old with mean difference of 1.27 and 3.43 respectively.

The results of the single factor ANOVA are the following: F value is 3.59 and critical F-value (F crit) is 3.13 at a significance level of 0.05. Since, the F value (3.59) obtained exceeds the critical value (3.13) this suggests that a significant difference exists between the age groups in terms of problem-solving skills. Moreover, the p-value associated with the F-test is equivalent to 0.033 which is below the typical significance level of 0.05, this implies a strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in problem-solving skills across different age groups. Thus, there is a significant difference in problem-solving skills among the age groups of 15, 16, and 17.

TABLE 20*ANOVA of Problem-solving in terms of Age*

Age	Mean	SD	Observation	df	F	F crit	p-value	Cohen's D
15	15.73	3.31	30					
16	13.57	4.24	35	69	3.59	3.13	0.033	0.58
17	17	2.83	5					

Problem 10. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the students across their profile in terms of gender?

Table 21 denotes a medium significant difference ($d = 0.54$) between female ($M = 17.33$, $SD = 2.19$) and male ($M = 17.33$, $SD = 4.54$) results of the reading comprehension with F -value = 5.111 and critical F -value = 3.982. Since, $5.111 > 3.982$ F -value is greater than the critical F -value this indicate that there is a significant difference in the gender of students in terms of their reading comprehension skills. Additionally, the p -value is 0.02 or $p < 0.05$, since the p -value is less than the level of significance, this implies a strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that female students performed significantly better or has a higher level of reading comprehension skills compared with male students with mean difference of 2.03. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference of the reading comprehension of the students in terms of gender is hereby rejected.

1.1. TABLE 21

ANOVA of Reading Comprehension in terms of Gender

Gender	Mean	SD	Observation	Df	F	F_{crit}	p -value	Cohen's D
Female	17.33	4.54	30	69	5.111	3.982	0.0270	0.54
Male	15.3	2.19	40					

Problem 11. Is there a significant difference in the problem-solving of the students across their profile in terms of gender?

Table 22 exhibits no medium significant difference ($d = 0.47$) between female ($M = 15.73$, $SD = 3.31$) and male ($M = 14$, $SD = 4.22$) results of the problem-solving skills with F -value = 3.461 and critical F -value = 3.982. Since, $3.461 < 3.982$ F -value is smaller than the critical F -value this indicate that there is no significant difference in the gender of students in terms of their problem-solving skills. Correspondingly, the p -value is 0.0671 or $p > 0.05$, since the p -value is greater than the level of significance, this implies strong evidence to support the null hypothesis. This indicates that both male and female students performed in problem-solving skills in some similar level. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference of the problem-solving of the students in terms of gender is hereby accepted.

TABLE 22

ANOVA of Problem-solving in terms of Gender

Gender	Mean	SD	Observation	df	F	F crit	p-value	Cohen's D
Female	15.73	4.22	30	69	3.461	3.982	0.0671	0.47
Male	14	3.31	40					

DISCUSSION

The study aims to examine the relationship between reading comprehension, problem solving and academic achievement of the students in the Saint Joseph College of Sindangan Incorporated S.Y 2023-2024. Before proceeding to the data gathering, a pilot test is conducted to eighteen (18) students who are not included in the identified participants of the study in order to examine the reliability and consistency of the research instrument (multiple-choice survey questionnaire) which is a researchers-made instrument. A survey is then conducted to seventy (70) Grade 10 students to gather essential information to answer the series queries in the statement of the problem. The statistical tools used in the study were Frequency Count and Percentage, PPMC, Regression, ANOVA and Cohen's D in analyzing and calculating the data gathered. Definitely, the results indicates that there is a significant relationship between reading comprehension and problem solving with correlation coefficient $r 0.63$ (moderately correlated); there is a significant relationship between reading comprehension and academic achievement with correlation coefficient $r 0.73$ (highly correlated); and there is a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and academic achievement with correlation coefficient $r 0.72$ (highly correlated). Moreover, the result reveals that there is a significant difference of reading comprehension in terms of the ages and gender of the students. Apart from that there is also a significant difference of problem-solving skills in terms of age, whereas results denotes that there is no significant difference in the problem-solving skills of students in terms of their gender.

Conclusions

This section summarizes the findings with regards to the connection between reading comprehension, problem-solving abilities, and academic performance and other insights that is related to the goals of the study. The conclusion is based on the answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age

Out of seventy (70) participants of the study, twenty-five (25) have an age of 15 years old, forty (40) has an age of 16 years old, and five (5) has an age of 17 years old, having 15 years of age as a majority age of the students in Grade 10 in SJCSI.

1.2. Gender

Among seventy (70) students who participated in the study, forty (40) is male and thirty (30) is female, having male as the most numbered gender in the sample size and it might be true in the population of Grade 10 students in SJCSI.

2. What is the level of reading comprehension skills of the students?

Of the seventy (70) participants, forty-one (41) got scores ranging from 17 – 20 (very proficient), twenty (20) got scores ranging from 13 – 16 (proficient), five (5) got scores ranging from 9 – 12 (somehow proficient), one (1) got scores ranging from 5 – 8 (less proficient), and three (3) got scores ranging from 0 – 4 (not proficient); with mean score of 16.17 (SD = 3.83). This signifies that majority of the students is proficient in terms of reading comprehension skills.

3. What is the level of Problem-Solving Skills of the students?

Out of the seventy participants of the study, twenty-nine (29) got scores ranging from 17 – 20 (superior), nineteen (20) got scores ranging from 13 – 16 (above average), sixteen (16) got scores ranging from 9 – 12 (average), four (4) got scores ranging from 5 – 8 (below average), and one (1) got scores ranging from 0 – 4 (poor); with mean score of 14.61 and SD of 3.91. This denotes that the majority of the students belong to the above average level of problem-solving skills.

4. What is the academic achievement of the students?

Of the seventy (70) participants, twenty-nine (29) got percentile scores ranging from 90 – 100 (outstanding), eighteen (18) got percentile scores ranging from 85 – 89 (very satisfactory), twelve (12) got percentile scores ranging from 80 – 84 (satisfactory), nine (9) got percentile scores ranging from 75 – 79 (less proficient), and two (2) got scores below 75 (did not meet the expectations); with mean percentile score of 86.43 and SD of 5.87. This implies that majority of the students has a very satisfactory academic achievement in English and Mathematics subjects.

5. Is there a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills of the students?

There is a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills of the students with correlation coefficient (r) of 0.63 which indicates a moderate correlation, with p-value of 5.15×10^{-9} (< 0.05). This indicates that as reading comprehension improves, so does the ability to do problem-solving. In addition, this suggests that students who possess stronger reading comprehension skills tend to also have better problem-solving abilities.

6. Is there a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and the academic achievement of the students?

There is a significant relationship between reading comprehension skills and the academic achievement of the students with correlation coefficient (r) of 0.73 which indicates a high correlation, with p-value of 1.56×10^{-15} (< 0.05). This high correlation suggests that as students' reading comprehension abilities improve, their academic achievement tends to show a corresponding improvement.

7. Is there a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and academic achievement of the students?

There is a significant relationship between problem-solving skills and the academic achievement of the students with correlation coefficient (r) of 0.72 which indicates a moderate correlation, with p-value of 5.12×10^{-7} (< 0.05). The implications of these highlight the importance of fostering and developing problem-solving skills as a means to positively enhance students' academic achievement.

8. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the students across their profile in terms of age?

There is a medium significant difference ($d = 0.70$) between the age groups: 15 years old ($M = 17.33$, $SD = 2.19$), 16 years old ($M = 14.83$, $SD = 4.64$) and 17 years old ($M = 18.6$, $SD = 1.52$) of the students' reading comprehension skills results, F-value of 5.06, F critical value of 3.13 and p-value of 0.00896 (p-value < 0.05). This means that 17 years old performed significantly better than 15- and 16-years old students with mean differences of 1.27 and 3.77 respectively. Further, this finding denotes the importance of considering age as a factor in understanding and addressing variations in reading comprehension skills among students.

9. Is there a significant difference in the problem-solving of the students across their profile in terms of age?

There is a medium significant difference ($d = 0.58$) between the age groups: 15 years old ($M = 15.73$, $SD = 3.31$), 16 years old ($M = 13.57$, $SD = 4.24$) and 17 years old ($M = 17$, $SD = 2.83$) of the students' problem-solving skills results, F-value of 3.59, F critical value of 3.14 and p-value of 0.033 (p-value < 0.05). This means that 17 years old performed significantly better than 15- and 16-years old students with mean differences of 1.27 and 3.43 respectively. Moreover, this signifies an importance of considering age as a factor in understanding and addressing the variations in problem-solving skills among students.

10. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the students across their profile in terms of gender?

There is a medium significant difference ($d = 0.54$) between the gender of the students Female ($M = 17.33$, $SD = 2.19$) and male ($M = 15.3$, $SD = 4.54$) of the students' reading comprehension skills results, F-value of 5.11, F critical value of 3.98 and p-value of 0.027 (p-value < 0.05). This means that female students performed significantly better or has a higher level of reading comprehension skills

than male students with mean difference of 2.03. Furthermore, this implies an importance of considering gender as a factor in understanding and addressing variations in reading comprehension skills among students.

11. Is there a significant difference in the problem-solving of the students across their profile in terms of gender?

There is no medium significant difference ($d = 0.47$) between the gender of the students Female ($M = 15.73$, $SD = 3.31$) and male ($M = 14$, $SD = 4.22$) of the students' problem-solving skills results, F-value of 3.46, F critical value of 3.98 and p-value of 0.067 (p-value > 0.05). This means that female students don't performed significantly better than male students, more likely they have similar level of performance in terms of problem-solving. Furthermore, this means that gender is not an important consideration to understand and address the variations in problem-solving skills among students.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of the study, the researchers would like to recommend the following:

1. Incorporate age-specific strategies: Since there is a significant difference in reading comprehension skills and problem-solving skills across different age groups, it is recommended to design instructional approaches that cater to the unique needs and abilities of students at different ages. This can help optimize their reading comprehension and problem-solving development.
2. Promote gender-inclusive approaches: While there is a significant difference in reading comprehension skills between male and female students; it is important to create an inclusive learning environment that supports the development of reading comprehension skills for all genders. Implementing various teaching strategies and providing equal opportunities for participation can help address any differences and inequalities.
3. Foster reading comprehension through cross-curricular activities: Recognizing the high correlation between reading comprehension skills and academic achievement, educators should emphasize the integration of reading comprehension strategies across different subjects. This can be achieved by incorporating reading materials, discussions, activities, and assignments that require critical thinking and comprehension in all disciplines. For example, English proficiency, Read-A-Tone activity, story mapping and making inferences activities.
4. Integrate problem-solving skills into the curriculum: Given the high correlation between problem-solving skills and academic achievement, it is vital and necessary to incorporate explicit instruction and practice opportunities for problem-solving skills across various subjects. This will equip students with transferable skills which are necessary for their development that can enhance their overall academic performance as well as their ability to solve and handle real problems.

5. Encourage collaborative problem-solving activities: Given the high correlation between problem-solving skills and academic achievement, educators should promote collaborative problem-solving activities that foster teamwork, communication, and critical thinking. This can be achieved through group projects, discussions, and problem-based learning approaches, allowing students to learn from each other and develop their problem-solving abilities.
6. Provide targeted support for students with lower proficiency levels: Students who exhibit lower reading comprehension and problem-solving skills should be identified, and targeted interventions should be implemented to address their specific needs. This may include additional instructional support, individualized learning plans, or remedial programs to help them improve their skills and bridge any gaps associated with those essential skills.
7. The school should provide professional development for teachers: To effectively support students' reading comprehension and problem-solving skills, teachers should receive ongoing professional development since teacher plays a vital role in developing the essential skills of the students, teachers should embodied the knowledge and competency necessary for the better learning. This can include workshops, seminars, or training sessions focused on instructional strategies, assessment techniques, and differentiation methods that promote these skills in the classroom.
8. Students should prioritize the development of their reading comprehension and problem-solving skills: Students should actively engage in activities to improve these skills, seek support when needed, collaborate with peers, and practice self-assessment and reflection, since learning is the responsibility of the students, it is not just the job of the teacher. Additionally, students should dwell in varied reading materials, develop time management, and study skills, and maintain motivation and persistence in their learning journey. By focusing on these aspects, students can enhance their academic achievement and acquire valuable skills for their future endeavors.
9. Conduct further research: While this study gives light on the relationship between reading comprehension, problem-solving, and academic achievement, further research is encouraged in order to explore additional factors that may influence these skills, highly suggested to have enough time frame in order to focus on this matter and can possibly find more insights relevant to the study. This could include investigating the impact of socioeconomic status, instructional methodologies, or cultural influences and many more to gain a more comprehensive understanding of student performance in these areas.

By implementing these recommendations, administrators and educators can create a conducive learning environment that fosters the development of reading comprehension and problem-solving skills, basically enhancing students' academic achievement that will of necessity in the educational growth of the students. Further, these

are just some of the series of recommendations drawn from the findings of the study, the school, policymakers, administrators or even the educators like teachers might take into accounts these or might have any additional insights to implement in the educational context to shape a worthwhile learning experience of the students that will contribute to the academic success and well-being of every individuals – the students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The success of this research endeavor requires not only efforts, expertise, knowledge, and diligence but also being able to follow through the ethical way of conducting research with honesty and integrity. This is taken into consideration to organize, respect and protect human rights especially the rights of the participants of the study. To render these ethical ways, the rights to self-determination, anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent were given emphasis and were carefully observed by the researchers. The researchers asked the permission of the school principal since the study will be conducted in the school itself and also the participants' consent was obtained before the data gathering session commences.

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